

IMPROVING STUDENTS' PROFICIENCY IN LEARNING ENGLISH FOR SPECIFIC PURPOSES AT NGHE AN COLLEGE OF ECONOMICS BY USING LANGUAGE LEARNING STRATEGIES - AN ACTION RESEARCH

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ABSTRACT

English for Specific Purposes (ESP) in Universities is obviously necessary in the time of integration. Since graduate students in Universities are people ready for employment, ESP has become one of the life-long property that they have to attain. Good English, especially English for Specific Purposes, can help them in finding a high-quality job, communicating with the international world, and accessing scientific and academic sources in their major fields. However, it is not easy for most students to study and master ESP. The research is conducted to find out what learning strategies that students at Nghe An College of Economics are using in learning ESP, what strategies contribute the most in their studying and then give them some recommendations to improve their studying in ESP using appropriate learning strategies.

Key words: English for Specific Purposes, learning strategies, outcome competences, economics...

1 INTRODUCTION

The importance of English cannot be denied and ignored these days. With the help of new technologies in the 21st century, English has been playing and showing its essential role in many fields of life including medicine, engineering, economics, business, literature, politics, agriculture, tourism and education, ect... It is not only a means but also a key to accessing the latest achievements of all fields in life. Further more, it's English that brings many countries in the World closer one another. Therefore, it is necessary for many Vietnamese to have a good knowledge of English to satisfy the growing needs in a developing country like Vietnam in the time of modernization and integration.

However, learning a language is a lifelong process and learning English, especially English for specific purposes, is not an exception. The success of learning a language can be influenced by many factors including learning motivation, learning materials, learning environment and learning strategies ect... Among the factors mentioned above, learning strategies have its own importance in the field of learning English in general and ESP in particular. As it is stated that Learning Strategies play an important (LLSs) role in learning a second language (L2). These are activities or special techniques to help learners develop language skills. Using appropriate

strategies helps learners grasp the form, function, and culture needed to understand the second language (Oxford, 1990).

ESP is a compulsory subject in Nghe An College of Economics. Students find it one of the most difficult subjects because of its large number of new words, long text and academic information. Being a teacher of English at Nghe An College of Economics, I am aware of my responsibility of helping the students improve their proficiency in learning ESP. And with the understanding of the important role of Language Learning Strategies in language learning, I started conducting the research "*Improving students' proficiency in learning English for Specific Purposes at Nghe An College of Economics by using Language Learning Strategies*".

This research was conducted to address the following research questions:

1. What types of language learning strategies are being used by students at Nghe An College of Economics while they are learning ESP? And what are their most frequently used language learning strategies
2. Which strategies have positive impacts on the students' process of studying ESP?
3. Do language learning strategies help improve students' proficiency in learning ESP?

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

Nowadays, it is widely acknowledged that learning strategies have become one of the main factors that help students to learn a second or foreign language successfully (Oxford 2003). This educational issue has been mainly tackled by many linguists and researchers. Many studies of second language learning (e.g. Green & Oxford, 1995; Griffiths & Parr, 2001; Oxford, 1990; Park, 1997; Wharton, 2000) have extensively documented how successful learners seem to use a wider variety of language learning strategies than unsuccessful learners. Meanwhile, several studies (e.g. Bruen, 2001; Cohen, 1998; Oxford, 1990; O'Malley & Chamot, 1993; Purpura, 1997; Shen, 2005; Wharton, 2000) have revealed that selecting appropriate strategies could enhance the learners' performance of second language learning. It is clear that the choices of strategies used by second language learners plays a vital role in second language learning. Consequently, students have been suggested using language learning strategies since LLS have the potential to be "an extremely powerful learning tool" (Oxford, 1990; Cohen, 1998; Chamot, 2001).

Being considered the "extremely powerful learning tool", Language Learning Strategies have been attracting linguists' and researchers' attention and have inspired in many fruitful researches since the last decade.

Despite the fact that numerous attempts have been made at defining language learning strategies, there are many authors who still think they are vague and difficult to identify and define (Ellis, 1997). Oxford (1990) describes them as "specific actions taken by the learner to make learning easier, faster, more enjoyable, more self-directed, more effective and more transferrable to new situations", whereas Nunan (1999) simply defines them as "mental processes which learners employ to learn and use the target language". For the aims of this study, LLSs will mean "the

specific actions employed by the learners for the purpose of accomplishing their language learning goals”.

LLSs vary widely and they are divided into distinct categories. Oxford (1990) distinguishes between direct (memory, cognitive and compensation) and indirect (metacognitive, affective and social) LLSs. Chamot (1990) divides LLSs into three main headings: cognitive strategies, metacognitive strategies and socio-affective strategies. For the objectives of the study, I applied the classification of Oxford (1990) to conduct my research.

The three groups of direct strategies are as follows:

- *Memory strategies*: - techniques specifically tailored to help the learners store new information in their memory and retrieve it later on, e.g. placing new words in context, using keywords and representing sounds in memory, etc.
- *Cognitive strategies*: - skills that allow learners to better comprehend and produce language in different ways, e.g. note-taking, repetition, summarizing text, etc.
- *Compensation strategies* – behaviors used to compensate and help them to employ the language, e.g. guessing while listening or reading, or using synonyms or paraphrasing while speaking or writing.

As opposed to direct strategies, “Indirect strategies provide indirect support for language learning through focusing, planning, evaluating, seeking opportunities, controlling anxiety, increasing cooperation and empathy, and other means” (Oxford, 1990). The three sets of indirect strategies are as follows:

- *Metacognitive strategies* – behaviors used for arranging, planning and evaluating one’s learning, e.g. overviewing and linking with already known material.
- *Affective strategies* – techniques which regulate emotional behaviors and motivation, e.g. using relaxation techniques, singing songs in a target language to lower one’s anxiety, etc.
- *Social strategies* – actions allowing better learner interaction with other people in the language learning process, e.g. asking questions, cooperating with peers, and developing empathy towards target language speaking people, etc.

3 MATERIAL AND METHODS

To address the research questions mentioned above, I applied a mixture of qualitative method and action research in the classroom.

3.1 Participants

A total of 188 students at Nghe An College of Economics participating in this study were asked to answer a widely used language learning strategy questionnaire, Oxford’s (1990) Strategy Inventory for Language learning (SILL) during their regular classes. Among the participants, 103 students were last-year students who have finished their ESP; and 85 students were third-year students who are learning their ESP. They were non-major in English language. They were major

in accounting and their ESP course was English for Accounting. Their ages were from 20 to 22 years old. The participants were in four classes at which I was teaching. The number of girls were more than boys.

3.2 Procedure of research

To fulfill the aims of the study, I applied a three-step cycle to do the research.

Step 1:

Before conducting an action research in the classroom, the researcher started a pilot study by doing a survey using questionnaires. The pilot study was conducted with the participation of 103 last-year students who had finished their ESP. The survey was accomplished with the aims of collecting the information about Language Learning Strategies, including types of language learning strategies being used by students; the strategies frequency and the impacts of strategies on students' studying. The questionnaires were designed into two parts. Part I was about some personal information. The personal information was compulsory for the purpose of the study. Part II contained the Strategy Inventory for Language Learning (SILL) developed by Oxford (1990) which consisted 50 items focused on the collecting information about students' learning strategies in learning ESP, especially in English for accounting. In order to get the most accurate data and to help the participants avoid misunderstanding, the 50-item questionnaires were translated into Vietnamese but kept the same total number of items and the arrangement of items. The students' final scores were also taken in to consideration in this step.

Step 2:

Having explored the strategies used by participants, I started my action research in the classroom. The participants in the action research were 85 third-year students who were taught ESP by me. Their ESP textbook was English for Accounting. The participants were, of course, non major in English. The participants were divided into 2 groups: control and experiment group. The scores in General English of two groups were not so different. The experiment group was asked to used the strategies which were most frequently used by good students during their process of learning ESP. Whereas, the control group learned ESP as usual, which meant that the researcher didn't know whether they used LLSs. The action research design that I chose was "post-test in both control and experiment groups".

Step 3:

Having finished the course, I asked two groups to do the same final test in order to check if the students' proficiency in learning ESP was improved when using language learning strategies.

3.3 Data collection and analysis

3.3.1. Data of Language learning strategies

In order to answer two first research questions, the SILL questionnaires were used during the study. The questionnaires employed a five point Likert-type scale and the participants were to choose from always to never. Scores 01, 02, 03, 04, 05 is for never, seldom, sometimes, usually,

always respectively. Spearman Brown formulas was adapted to verify the reliability of the data collected in survey through the questionnaire. The formulas was shown as following:

$$r_{SB} = 2 * r_{hh} / (1 + r_{hh}) \quad (1)$$

(r_{SB} : Reliability Spearman-Brown)

(r_{hh} : Coefficient of correlation between odd and even)

$r_{SB} \geq 0,7$	Reliable data	(2)
$r_{SB} < 0,7$	Unreliable data	

Coefficient of correlation between odd and even (r_{hh}) is calculated in EXCEL using following function:

$$r_{hh} = \text{correl}(\text{array1}, \text{array2})$$

(array 1: total even scores, array 2: total odd scores)

A descriptive analysis of the SILL items was also performed by calculating Mode, Median, Mean and Standard deviation. These values are calculated in EXCEL using functions below:

VALUES	FOMULAS	(3)
Mode	=mode(number1,number2,...)	
Median	=median(number1,number2,...)	
Mean	=average(number1,number2,...)	
Standard deviation	=stdev(number1,number2,...)	

3.3.2 Data of efficiency in learning ESP

To evaluate how the participants' efficiency in learning ESP improved, the same test was employed in both group, control and experiment. The participants took the test at the end of the course. Their scores were compared to check and evaluate the improvement of their efficiency in learning ESP.

Firstly, the scores of control group and experiment group were described by Mode, Median, Mean and Standard Deviation using the functions (2) above.

Secondly, the Independent T-test was adapted to compare the difference of the two groups so that I could determine the Probability which helped me verify if the mean value between control group and experiment group was random or meaningful.

Formulas to calculate Probability in EXCEL as following:

$$P = \text{ttest}(\text{array1}, \text{array2}, \text{tail}, \text{type}) \quad (4)$$

(array1: score column of control group, array 2: score column of experiment group, tail=1, type=3)

Tail = 1(Hypothesis was directional)

Type = 3 (Unequal variance)

$P \leq 0,05$	The value is meaningful
$P > 0.05$	The value is not meaningful, it may be random

(5)

Thirdly, I applied Cohen (1998) formulas to calculate effect size (ES) of the value. The ES was used to determine if the action had effect or not. The formulas is shown as follow:

$$SMD = \frac{\text{Mean value of experiment group} - \text{Mean value of control group}}{\text{Standard deviation of control}} \quad (6)$$

(SDM: Standard Median Deviation)

This value was used to check if the effect size of the action. If the effect size was above 0,50 (ES>0,50), the action should be used. The effect size was explained in the criteria table of Cohen (1998) as follow:

SMD	Effect size
>100	Very big
0,80 - 100	Big
0,50 – 0,79	Average
0,20 – 049	Small
< 0,20	Very small

(7)

4 FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Research question 1 and 2

What language learning strategies are being used by students at Nghe An College of Economics during their process of learning ESP? And what are their most frequently used language learning strategies?

In order to address the research question 1 and 2, I applied a pilot study with the participation of last year students who had finished their ESP course. The participants were asked to answer the questionnaires based on SILL (Oxford,1990). After collecting the questionnaires, I started to verify the reliability of the data collected using formula (1) and then described the data by Mode,

Median, Mean and Standard deviation on EXCEL using the functions in (3)

The results of the pilot study was shown in the table 1 below:

Table 1: The reliability and description of SILL questionnaire

TT	Statement	Mod	Mean	Med	SD	Type
1	I think of relationships between what I already know and new things I learn in theSL.	3	3.4	3	0.6	Memory
2	I use new SL words in a sentence so I can remember them.	3	3.3	3	0.8	
3	I connect the sound of a new SL word and an image or picture of the word to help me remember theword.	3	3.4	3	1.2	
4	I remember a new SL word by making a mental picture of a situation in which the word might beused.	3	3.7	4	1.0	
5	I use rhymes to remember new SLwords.	3	2.4	2	0.7	
6	I use flashcards to remember new SLwords.	2	2.7	2	0.8	
7	I physically act out new SLwords.	3	2.4	3	1.2	
8	I review SL lessonsoften.	3	2.4	3	1.2	
9	I remember new SL words or phrases by remembering their location on the page, on the board, or on a streetsign	3	3.7	4	1.1	
10	I say or write new SL words severaltimes.	5	4.2	4	0.9	Cognitivestrategies
11	I try to talk like native SLspeakers.	3	3.7	3	1.0	
12	I practice the sounds ofSL.	3	3.6	4	0.7	
13	I use the SL words I know in differentways.	4	3.9	4	0.7	
14	I start conversations in SL	4	3.4	4	0.9	
15	I watch SL language TV shows spoken in SL or go to movies spoken inSL.	2	2.3	2	0.7	
16	I read for pleasure in theSL.	3	2.7	3	0.9	
17	I write notes, messages, letters, or reports in theSL	2	2.5	2	0.7	
18	I first skim an SL passage (read over the passage quickly) then go back and read carefully.	3	3.1	3	0.8	

TT	Statement	Mod	Mean	Med	SD	Type
19	I look for words in my own language that are similar to new words in theSL.	2	2.6	2	1.1	
20	I try to find patterns in the SL	2	2.4	2	0.9	
21	I find the meaning of an SL word by dividing it into parts that I understand.	2	2.5	2	1.2	
22	I try not to translate word forward	4	2.6	2.5	1.3	
23	I make summaries of information that I hear or read in theSL	2	1.9	2	1.1	
24	To understand unfamiliar SL words, I makeguesses	2	2.4	2	1.1	Compensation strategies
25	When I can't think of a word during a conversation in the SL, I use gestures.	5	3.5	3	1.4	
26	I make up new words if I do not know the right ones in theSL.	5	4.2	5	1.4	
27	I read SL without looking up every newword.	5	3.5	5	1.8	
28	I try to guess what the other person will say next in theSL.	1	3	3	1.8	
29	If I can't think of an SL word, I use a word or phrase that means the samething	5	4.2	5	0.9	Metacognitive strategies
30	I try to find as many ways as I can to use mySL	5	4.1	5	1.0	
31	I notice my SL mistakes and use that information to help me do better	5	4.2	5	0.9	
32	I pay attention when someone is speakingSL	5	4.1	5	1.1	
33	I try to find out how to be a better learner ofSL	5	4.6	5	0.7	
34	I plan my schedule so I will have enough time to studySL	4	4.1	4	0.8	
35	I look for people I can talk to inSL.	4	3.5	4	0.7	
36	I look for opportunities to read as much as possible inSL	3	3.2	3	06	
37	I have clear goals for improving my SLskills	3	3.3	3	0.7	
38	I think about my progress in learningSL	3	3.3	3	0.9	
39	I try to relax whenever I feel afraid of usingSL.	4	3.4	4	1.1	Affe ctive

TT	Statement	Mod	Mean	Med	SD	Type
40	I encourage myself to speak SL even when I am afraid of making a mistake	2	3.1	3	1.0	
41	I give myself a reward or treat when I do well inSL.	2	2.9	2	1.5	
42	I notice if I am tense or nervous when I am studying or usingSL	2	3.4	3	1.2	
43	I write down my feelings in a language learningdairy.	2	2.5	2	0.9	
44	I talk to someone else about how I feel when I am learningSL.	3	2.4	3	1.2	
45	If I do not understand something in SL, I ask the other person to slow down or say it again	3	2.4	3	1.2	
46	I ask SL speakers to correct me when Italk.	3	3.7	4	1.1	Social
47	I practice SL with otherstudents.	5	4.2	4	0.9	
48	I ask for help from SLspeakers.	3	3.7	3	1.0	
49	I ask questions inSL.	3	3.6	4	0.7	
50	I try to learn about the culture of SLspeakers.	4	3.9	4	0.7	
rBS		0,72				

According to the values in table 1 above and basing on the criteria in (2), the data about SILL collected were **RELIABALE** because the reliability coefficient was above 0.70. The descriptive analysis of the SILL items was also performed to answer the research questions 1 and 2. Generally, an item with mean score greater than 3.5 indicated that the language learning strategy which had been described in the item was in the high frequency of use; an item with mean score between 2.5 to 3.5 indicated the strategy was in the medium frequency of use; and an item with mean score smaller than 2.4 indicated a low frequency of use of that particular strategy (Oxford, 1990). As far as two first research questions are concerned, we could see that items 4, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 26, 29, 30, 31, 32, 33, 34, 46, 47, 48, 49, 50. Were strategies in the high frequency of use, which indicated that students used these strategies more often than others. The items 15(M=2.3) and 23(M=1.9) were below 2.4 and, and were in the low frequency of use. The last items ranged from 3.5 to 2.4 and, consequently, were in the medium frequency of use. The types of the strategies that the students used the most frequently were centred in social, metacognitive and cognitive strategies. These strategies were also used by good students among the participants. (The criteria used to define if the participants were good or bad were their final scores in ESP. The ones with their final score above 7.0 were define good students. The scores were collected with the help of Training Department and Department of Testing and Quality Assurance).

4.2 Research question 3

For finding the answer for research question 3, the researcher applied an action research in classroom. The action research was accomplished by the participation of 85 third-year students who were studying ESP at the college. 40 of the participants were in control group, and the left 45 were in the experiment group. The participants in experiment group were recommended in advance some of the most frequent learning strategies that the good students had used during their process of learning ESP. Lesson plans, teaching and learning activities, students' further practices were all designed in a special nature so that students in experiment group could make use of the learning strategies recommended. The strategies which were used the most frequently by good students were shown clearly in table 2 following:

Table 2: The most frequent Language Learning Strategies

Item	Strategy Inventory for Language learning	Mean
9	I remember new SL words or phrases by remembering their location on the page, on the board, or on a streetsign.	4.2
26	I make up new words if I do not know the right ones in theSL	4.2
29	If I can't think of a SL word, I use a word or phrase that means the same thing.	4.2
30	I try to find as many ways as I can to use mySL	4.1
31	I notice my SL mistakes and use that information to help me do better	4.2
32	I pay attention when someone is speakingSL.	4.1
33	I try to find out how to be a better learner ofSL	4.6
34	I plan my schedule so I will have enough time to study SL.	4.1
47	I practice SL with other students.	4.2

Here are some examples for further practices related to strategies recommended:

Item 9: Ask students to complete a real contract, a bill, a receipt, or a balance sheet. The missing words were often new words or phrases.

Item 26: Ask students to make new words by using affixation

Item 29: Ask students to guess the new words or phrases from explanations given.

Item 30: Ask students to express an idea in many ways.

Item 31: Ask students to find the errors and self-correct, or peer-correct the errors

Item 32: Ask students to listen to some of the real short conversations concerning to the lessons being learned, then ask them to repeat or summary the content of the conversations.

Item 33: Ask students to find on the internet as much as possible the documents, pictures, conversations or videos concerning to learning ESP.

Item 34: Ask students to make a schedule for each lesson.

Item 47: Ask students to role play and make their own videos or clips.

The action research lasted 3 months during the ESP course. When the course finished, students in both groups were asked to do the same test. The scores of the test were used to check if learning strategies could improve students’ proficiency in learning ESP. The total students were not the same, which made 5 tests not taken into data analysis. The tests were discarded randomly. The data collected in the action research were described as shown in the tables below:

Table 3: Data description (post-act test)

Value	Control group	Experiment group
Mode	5	7
Median	5	6
Mean	5,2	6,2
Standard deviation	1,42	1,41

Table 4: Independent T-test verification

	Control group (a)	Experiment group (b)
Mean	5,2	6,2
Difference value (b-a)	1,0	
P	0.0014	
ES	0.69	

The answer to the last research questions were quite straightforward. According to (5) and (7), the researcher could come to a conclusion that applying Language Learning Strategies DO IMPROVE students’ proficiency. The probability was very low (P=0.0014), which meant the difference between the mean of two groups was not random. The Effect Size (ES=0.69) was on top of the average range, which meant the action had an average effect.

5 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

5.1 Conclusion

As it was seen through the theory presented in the study, LLSs are among the main factors that help determine how and how well our students learn a second language. The results of the study

have helped teachers and students have a better understanding about the nature, types and patterns of using strategies in achieving different language skills. The results also indicate that students should use LLSs in learning a language, especially in English and English for Specific Purposes. These strategies enable them to work consciously on their learning ESP and to interact frequently with others in English. In terms of language proficiency, the study reveals strategies that students should choose during their learning ESP including social, metacognitive and cognitive strategies. As shown in the pilot study, low-level students often use memory strategies whereas higher-level students prefer using a variety of cognitive, metacognitive and social strategies. Oxford (2003) agreed that drills, rote memorization, dialogue memorization, repetition and kinetics are associated with the grammatical approach, which are not always feasible to promote L2 proficiency in advance stage. They are better used in early stages of language learning process.

To sum up, one of the main goals of language education, especially in ESP education, is to create students far more motivated, engaged, and independent that take the responsibility for their own development in language learning, and as a result, they are able to become autonomous learners. To gain this goal, the teachers should weave leaning strategies into their curriculum. Meanwhile, the students should have their suitable strategies during their learning process.

5.2 Recommendations

5.2.1 For teachers

It's obvious that LLSs are play a key role in language learning. Therefore, the teachers' role in strategy training is an important one. English teachers should design their classroom activities which related to the strategies of social, cognitive, and metacognitive, in the process of teaching ESP so that students might have opportunities to try and apply learning strategies. Students should be guided, observed and differentiated in ESP classrooms rather than being taught the target language word by word or grammatical rules. For accounting students, it is important for them to be able to present their ideas or exchange their opinions of the accounting rules among the countries, the ways of building a contract, the design of a blance sheet and so on. In the ESP classroom, information is usually transferred by reading a text or preparing a presentation which involves at least two or four skills. Therefore, it is appropriate for teachers to use an integrated skill approach. Having this problem in mind, it is clear that teachers should help their students by promoting language learning strategies and stressing their importance. In other words, students should be informed of the existence of strategies and shown how to use them in learning English for specific purpose in general and English of Accounting in particular. Teachers need to show less successful students how more successful students combine and use the strategies. Teachers should have an understanding of the students' strengths and weaknesses. Since teaching is not a one-way activity but an interative process, so it is important for teacher to have good reltionships with students. "When students take more responsibility, more learning occurs and both teachers and learners feel more successful" (Oxford, 1990).

5.2.2 For students

For whatever reason, students are still the decisive role in their learning process. Therefore, they must be active in learning. They must have their own strategies that are relevant to their situation and level. Memorize or review are necessary, however, they are not the best strategies to improve their proficiency in ESP. They should develop their strategies related to cognitive, metacognitive or soacial aspects.

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